

THE STEP FROM SEASONAL TOURISM TO SUSTAINABILITY: IN THE CONTEXT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This research paper mainly discusses several factors to prevent seasonality and ways to reduce it. In Uzbekistan, due to the pandemic, climate change and other factors, the level of seasonality in the tourism sector has increased, which may cause a decrease in the flow of tourists, a slowdown in the activity of tourist facilities, the cessation of the activities of some travel agencies, and the slow development of the economy. In order to prevent such processes, several things can be done. By further developing the types of rural, desert, gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan and using the available resources to the maximum, we will achieve a reduction in seasonality.*

Keywords: *tourism, seasonality, Uzbekistan, village tourism, desert tourism, gastronomic tourism, tourist resources.*

Аннотация. *В данной научной статье рассматриваются несколько факторов предотвращения сезонности и способы её снижения. В Узбекистане из-за пандемии, изменения климата и других факторов уровень сезонности в туристическом секторе увеличился, что может привести к снижению потока туристов, замедлению деятельности туристических объектов, прекращению работы некоторых туристических агентств и замедленному развитию экономики. Для предотвращения таких процессов можно предпринять ряд мер. Развивая сельский, пустынный и гастрономический туризм в Узбекистане, а также максимально используя имеющиеся ресурсы, мы сможем добиться снижения сезонности.*

Ключевые слова: *туризм, сезонность, Узбекистан, сельский туризм, пустынный туризм, гастрономический туризм, туристические ресурсы.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu ilmiy maqolada mavsumiylikni oldini olish omillari va uni kamaytirish usullari muhokama qilinadi. O‘zbekistonda pandemiya, iqlim o‘zgarishi va boshqa omillar tufayli turizm sohasida mavsumiylik darajasi oshdi, bu esa sayyohlar oqimining kamayishiga, turistik obyektlar faoliyatining sekinlashishiga, ayrim sayyohlik agentliklarining faoliyatini to‘xtatishiga va iqtisodiyot rivojlanishining sustlashishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Bunday jarayonlarning oldini olish uchun bir qator chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirish mumkin. O‘zbekistonda qishloq, cho‘l va gastronomik turizm turlarini yanada rivojlantirish va mavjud resurslardan maksimal darajada foydalanish orqali mavsumiylikni kamaytirishga erishamiz.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *turizm, mavsumiylik, O‘zbekiston, qishloq turizmi, cho‘l turizmi, gastronomik turizm, turistik resurslar.*

Introduction

For many years, tourism has been one of the most important sectors that bring great benefits to society. Many people are provided with work through tourism. Tourism has become the most important industry not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world. However, some problems and factors have caused seasonality in tourism. For example, an increase in air temperature in

summer and cold weather in winter affects the flow of tourists in some countries. Based on the climate of Uzbekistan, 75% of tourists visit mainly in autumn and spring to see our rich historical and cultural heritage.

Figure 1:

Touristic arrivals to Uzbekistan during the months

Note: (Source: Statistics agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Not only the weather, but there are other factors as well. The pandemic has also had a significant impact on tourism around the world, which means that this sector needs to be further developed. During the pandemic, in 2020, 1.5 million tourists visited Uzbekistan, and in 2023, this figure reached almost 7 million.

Figure 2:

Touristic arrivals to Uzbekistan in 2018-2023 years

Note: (Source: Statistics agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

This diagram analyses the number of tourist arrivals from 2018 to 2023 in Uzbekistan. As you can see, the number of tourists decreased during 2020-2021 pandemic.

There are several strategies to prevent tourism seasonality in Uzbekistan. If we make maximum use of all available tourist resources, we can achieve the desired results. Avoiding seasonality and transitioning to sustainable tourism will definitely take time and money. For this, the development of rural, gastronomic, pasture, desert, and other types of tourism, improvement

of tourism infrastructures, and having our own tourism brands are the main steps for us. In order to prevent seasonality and further develop tourism in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to make maximum use of tourist resources, produce tourist products, and introduce new tourist innovations. It is possible to attract more tourists by developing village tourism in Uzbekistan, because they want to know the local people in the village, their way of life, what they do. In Ostonov’s article “Perspective of rural tourism development in Uzbekistan” he states, “Currently, there are 10865 villages in Uzbekistan. Each of these villages has a unique tourist destination. It is untenable that the organization and development of tourism, which is widely used in tourism activities in our country, especially in rural areas, have a great impact on our socioeconomic life” (2018). Rural tourism is gradually developing in Uzbekistan. As mentioned, rural tourism has a great impact on the socio-economic life of our country. Many tour agencies are doing different things in the villages. But this is not enough. Many tourists are very interested in the lifestyle, living conditions, activities and culture of visited nation. This means that we need to further develop rural tourism. What exactly do we mean by development? What can tourists do in the village? Here are some exercises:

1. Show the processes of beekeeping and honey extraction. This is definitely an interesting process for everyone. Tourists who live in the city are really interested in seeing the process.
2. Planting and picking fruits and vegetables. Most people only eat fruits and vegetables. Few numbers of people know how to grow it or how to harvest it. For others, it might be fun.
3. Learning how to fish. There are also some ways to catch fish and it is a hobby for many people. In addition, fishing is very beneficial for the human nervous system.

According to “Factors for success in rural tourism development”, “One of the most popular nontraditional rural development strategies has been tourism and its associated entrepreneurship opportunities because of tourism’s ability to bring in dollars and to generate jobs and support retail growth”. (Wilson, 2001) As mentioned, rural tourism can provide employment to many people, which also affects the growth of the economy. At the same time, in the improvement of rural tourism, it is necessary to mention the process of improving the infrastructure there. It is necessary to improve the condition of the roads leading to the village, to make transportation and accommodation convenient for travelers. In addition, I think that interesting meetings and conversations between local residents and tourists should be held. Promotion of rural tourism is also important. This task must be performed by travel agencies or other private agencies. Because tourists do not know where there is a tourist village. We can inform them through advertising. In addition, we can further develop this industry through special tour packages, privileges, and discounts for going to the village.

We can develop gastronomic tourism by conveying to tourists the preparation of national dishes, their origin, and unique taste. In his work “Ways to reduce seasonality in the tourism market of Uzbekistan”, Kamolov mentions that “Currently, many countries are developing gastronomic tourism. Because every country has its own food and drinks. Our region is no exception. Food-related tourism is a famous category of tourism that involves visiting food producers, food festivals, restaurants, and special sites in order to taste a certain type of food, see a food being manufactured, or eat food made by a renowned chef” (2020). Through the development of gastronomic tourism, it is possible not only to increase the potential of tourism and the economy, but also to promote our unique culinary experience to the world. The fact that representatives of other countries try and promote our national dishes such as pilaf, manti, somsa, and halim in their regions creates a great opportunity for the development of the tourism potential of our country. To

do this, we need to establish and develop several processes. There are some strategies for developing gastronomic tourism.

Figure 3:

As an example, we can say that "Shirin tourism village" is operating in Vobkent district of Bukhara region. There you can see the process of preparation of "danakshorak" from apricot kernels by local residents and you can try making it yourself. Currently, French tourists are very interested in this activity.

In Nistoreanu, Nicodim and Diaconescu's article "Gastronomic tourism-stages and evolution" they mention, "Culinary tourism is an important and growing component in the big picture of the cultural tourism market. This unique form of tourism introduces tourists to a world of flavors, savors, and traditions associated with the preparation, serving and eating of food and drinks" (2018). The national dish of each country can become a special business card of tourism of that country. By promoting culinary skills and national cooking processes among representatives of other nationalities, we show our brand to them. Promotion of national products and food, i.e. advertising, is important for this sector. Only if we promote gastronomic tourism in tour agents, travel magazines and the like others can learn about it. If one tourist comes and tries soup or national somsa and other dishes and recommends it to others, and those people who were recommended come and taste it and recommend it to others. You will see that a complete chain will appear. This chain will certainly lead to a rise in the number of tourists, the development of tourism, and even greater increase in attention to our country.

Most land of Uzbekistan is desert, and we can further improve tourism by making maximum use of the tourist resources available there. According to Kamolov, he states, "Uzbekistan's deserts are sweltering and limitless, blazing and scorched by the sun. They cover more than half of the country's land area and are regarded as difficult living conditions in Central Asia. Deserts extend from the republic's northwestern border and progressively recede to the east" (2023). We know that most of Uzbekistan consists of a desert zone. This means a great opportunity for desert tourism. Desert tourism is one of the areas that we need to develop. Because in rare cases we can see tourism facilities established in the desert. We can put an end to seasonality by starting and developing some activities even in the hot season.

Figure 4:

Tourism Facilities established in the desert.

As you can see, we have a lot of options. It is important to be able to make maximum use of our tourist resources. And the introduction and development of various activities mentioned above will pave the way to turn desert tourism into the most profitable industry.

In Mavlonov, Mirzoeva and Kalandarova’s article “The Desert Tourism and Opportunities for its Development (On the Example of Bukhara Region)” they mention, “The territory of Uzbekistan consists of temperate and subtropical desert zones. The temperate deserts include the Ustyurt Plateau, the northern foothills of the Amu Darya, and the subtropical deserts include the Amudarya delta, Kyzylkum, Lower Zarafshan, and the foothills of the Kashkadarya foothills” (2020). We only know the desert names that we have. But we hardly hear or know that they use those lands for some touristic purposes. Our goal is to use these lands correctly and rationally. The development of desert tourism can open the way to new prospects. For example, the tourist center "Bukhara Desert Oasis" has started its work in Bukhara region. This center alone caused an increase in the number of tourists in Bukhara within one year and rose attention to desert tourism. You can see buildings built in historical style. This environment can really give you the spirit of that era. In addition, you will witness a beautiful view of the sunset and sunrise in a hot air balloon. The most interesting thing is that you will find all this in the middle of the desert. This tourist object was built in the desert. We can also develop this industry by building similar tourist centers in other places.

Conclusion

Since our goal is to reduce and prevent seasonality in Uzbekistan, considering the available tourist resources, factors, and activities today, we will implement these practices for the next period. We have considered several measures aimed at preventing seasonal tourism. That's not all. We have more opportunities and resources. We have met only a few. In fact, seasonal tourism is one of the most important aspects to focus on. Cooperation with local companies, state agencies, travel agencies, investors, businessmen, entrepreneurs for the development of rural tourism, desert tourism, gastronomy tourism will be an important foundation for the future of Uzbekistan's tourism. In addition, in order to promote tourism across all seasons, it is essential to intensify marketing and advertising campaigns both domestically and internationally. Effective promotion through digital platforms, media, international exhibitions, and collaborations with global influencers will raise awareness about the diverse tourism opportunities available year-round in Uzbekistan. We hope that there will be tourists in the villages, in the remote and endless deserts, even in the hottest and coldest times.

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